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“I’ll stop talking now”: Decreased interaction length in Mixed-Sex Interpersonal Interactions
as Response to Objectification

Gemma Sáez¹, Abigail R. Riemer², Inmaculada Valor Segura³ and Francisca Expósito³

¹Universidad Loyola Andalucía, ²Carroll University, ³Universidad de Granada

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Author’s note:

Corresponding author:

Inmaculada Valor-Segura, ivalor@ugr.es

CIMCYC (Mind, Brain and Behavior Research Center). Department of Social Psychology,
Faculty of Psychology, University of Granada, Campus Universitario de Cartuja, s/n, 18071,
Granada (Spain).

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This experiment explored behavioral consequences of interpersonal objectification. In an actual interaction with an objectifying man, women (N = 91) perceived the interaction as less pleasant, reducing the amount of time they spent interacting with the male objectifier compared to a neutral interaction. Moreover, the effect of the objectifying behavior on women's unpleasant perceptions of the interaction was mediated by the feeling of being treated as a sex object. This work demonstrates the consequences of an objectifying interaction at an interpersonal level.

Key words: Enjoyment of Sexualization, Mixed-Sex Interpersonal Interactions, Self-silencing, Sexism, Sexual Objectification

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“I’ll stop talking now”: Decreased interaction length in mixed-sex interpersonal interactions as a response to objectification

Over twenty years ago, objectification theory debuted to explain how frequent and pervasive experiences of sexualization shape women’s mental health (Fredrickson & Roberts, 1997). As a result, a plethora of research has examined the myriad intrapersonal mental health consequences of internalizing these objectifying perspectives (Roberts, Calogero, & Gervais, 2018). Yet, objectification occurs interpersonally through body evaluations and unwanted sexual advances, often perpetrated by men, leading women to experience negative psychological and social consequences (Fairchild & Rudman, 2008; Kozee, Tylka, Augustus-Horvath, & Denchik, 2007). For instance, Garcia, Earnshaw and Quinn (2016) showed that objectification from an unknown man detrimentally affects women’s perceptions of the interaction, cognitive performance and career aspirations. Consequently, theoretical calls have been put forth to examine objectification as it unfolds within actual interactions (Gervais, Sáez, Riemer, & Klein, 2020). In attempts to expand current understanding of how objectification shapes women’s behaviors within interactions, the current study examined how women perceive objectifying interactions, including their perceptions of and interest in interacting with objectifying men.

Reoccurring experiences of interpersonal objectification increase women’s likelihood of engaging in self-objectification. When women self-objectify, they internalize a third person’s perspective of themselves, thinking more about their appearance than their own thoughts, feelings, and desires, laying the groundwork for mental health issues (Fredrickson & Roberts, 1997). This internalized objectification shapes how women think about themselves during interactions as well as how women interact. For instance, when women self-objectify, they become more passive, justifying the system that oppresses them (Calogero, 2013), and speak less (Saguy, Quinn, Dovidio, & Pratto, 2010). Together these

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findings suggest that objectification leads women to behave in ways that confirm they are a sexual object instead of an active agent.

Negative consequences of objectification might suggest that women would perceive and respond to objectifying sources negatively; however, research is mixed. For instance, in an interactive experiment conducted by Teng, Chen, Poon, and Zhang (2010), women who experienced objectification reported perceiving the objectifying man as less likeable and were less willing to affiliate with him. Yet, an interactive experiment conducted by Gervais, Vescio and Allen (2011) revealed that when objectified, women reported greater liking and increased desire to interact with an objectifying man. These mixed findings are in line with recent suggestions of the importance of considering women's attitudes about being sexualized. For example, Riemer, Allen, Gullickson and Gervais (2020) found that women high in enjoyment of sexualization perceived objectifying commentary complimenting their appearance more positively than women low in enjoyment of sexualization. These findings suggest that women's impression of the objectifying man was determined by the extent to which they enjoy sexualization, revealing that women's perceptions of objectifying interactions may be more nuanced than originally assumed.

In mixed-sex interactions, gender norms prescribe women a submissive role, prioritizing men's feelings (Norris, Nurius, & Dumeff, 1996). Because women are socialized to maintain relationships with men, women often engage in self-silencing, in which they put men's needs first by not communicating their own thoughts, feelings, and desires (Jack & Dill, 1992). For instance, many women report difficulty in verbally confronting sexist remarks from men (Swim & Hyers, 1999). When experiencing sexual objectification, women may actively avoid and limit their interactions with the objectifying man in attempts to minimize the costs of confronting.

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In order to provide a comprehensive view of the negative consequences of being objectified, it is important to understand how women perceive and respond to these experiences. Given previous suggestions of the importance of women's attitudes toward sexualized attention (Riemer et al., 2020), the current work controlled for women's enjoyment of sexualization. We hypothesized that women would perceive an interaction with a man as less pleasant (Hypothesis 1) and spend less time talking to him (Hypothesis 2) if he objectified her relative to if he did not. Moreover, we hypothesized that the effect of experiencing objectification on women's perception of the interaction as pleasant, and on interaction length, would be mediated by feelings of being treated as a sexual object (Hypothesis 3 and 4 respectively).

Method

One hundred and three undergraduate women participated; 12 who did not identify as heterosexual were excluded, leaving a total of 91 participants¹ (age: $M = 21.24$, $SD = 2.36$, range = 18-33). Participants were compensated with 5 Euros or course credit for participating in, "*Interpersonal relationships and communication skills*" Ethics approval was obtained prior to recruitment.

Upon arrival to the lab, participants were randomly assigned to an objectification ($N = 46$) or control condition ($N = 45$) and informed they would be interacting with another participant in an interview context to form an impression of them. Following informed consent, participants were guided to a room with a male confederate. Once seated facing the confederate, participants were led to believe they were randomly assigned to play the role of the interviewee, although this was predetermined and consistent across participants. The research assistant then left the room and the male confederate began to interview the participant from a list of interview questions.

¹ A sensitivity analysis conducted using G*power (Faul, Erdfelder, Lang, & Buchner, 2009) suggests a sample size of 91 participants provided the ability to detect medium-to-large effects ($f_s = .25-.40$).

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Objectification manipulation. Relying on a similar procedure as Gervais and colleagues (2011), a male confederate unknown to participants delivered the objectification manipulation while conducting the interview. The confederate was the same 25-year-old man in all trials, and he was rated as average in attractiveness ($M = 4.02$, $SD = 1.4$ on a 7-point scale) by participants. Although impossible to keep him blind to condition, the confederate was unaware of variables of interest and hypotheses. Moreover, following the procedure of Gervais and colleagues (2011), he was systematically trained over the course of 3 weeks on how to consistently deliver the gaze (i.e., location and length) and commentary while in a neutral posture.

During the interview, the confederate asked the participant five questions (detailed in the supplemental material). In the objectification condition, the confederate delivered a head to waist body gaze when the participant entered the room, gazed at the participant's chest for two seconds while she responded to the first, third, and fifth questions, and at the conclusion of the interview commented, "By the way you look very good". In the control condition, the confederate maintained eye contact during the interaction, nodding his head during her responses, and at the conclusion of the interview commented, "By the way, you did very good". Immediately after this comment the confederate opened the door to signal the interview had concluded. After the interaction, the participant returned to another room to complete measures².

Length of the interaction. The research assistant was trained to precisely time the interaction; starting a stopwatch immediately after leaving the room from giving instructions to the participant and confederate, stopping as soon as the door was opened by the confederate (indicating the interaction ended). Importantly, the duration of the time the confederate spent talking during the interaction was identical independent of condition,

² Participants also completed additional measures that were not central to the current investigation.

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meaning that interaction length is uniquely dependent upon the time participants spent talking ($M_{\text{Seconds whole group}} = 125.41, SD = 36.67$).

Enjoyment of sexualization. Participants self-reported the extent to which they enjoy sexualized attention using the translated version of the Enjoyment of Sexualization Scale (ESS; Liss, Erchull, & Ramsey, 2011). Specifically, women rated their agreement with eight statements (e.g., I want men to look at me) using a 1 (*disagree strongly*) to 6 (*agree strongly*) scale. Responses were averaged ($M_{\text{whole group}} = 3.26, SD = 0.99; \alpha = .86$) and treated as a covariate to control for underlying individual differences in general attitudes about sexualized attention.

Perceived interaction pleasantness. Using a Likert-scale from 1 (*totally disagree*) to 7 (*totally agree*), participants reported on the extent to which they liked doing the task with the confederate, how comfortable they felt during the task with the confederate, and the extent to which they would like to see the confederate again. Pleasantness scores were calculated as the mean of the three items; higher scores indicate that participants perceived the interaction as pleasant ($M_{\text{whole group}} = 4.68, SD = 1.38; \alpha = .80$).

Feeling sexually objectified. Participants reported on the extent to which they felt as if they were being treated as a sex object during their interaction using a Likert-scale from 1 (*totally disagree*) to 7 (*totally agree*) ($M_{\text{whole group}} = 2.29, SD = 1.99$).

Manipulation check. Participants were asked to rate the extent to which they felt the confederate was focused on her body ($M_{\text{whole group}} = 3.05, SD = 1.93$) using a 1 (*totally disagree*) to 7 (*totally agree*) scale.

Results

Independent samples *t*-tests revealed main effects of condition on the manipulation check, $t(1, 74.73) = -5.12, p < .001, d = -1.08$. Women in the objectification condition reported that the confederate focused more on her body ($M = 3.96, SD = 2.05$) than women in

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the control condition ($M = 2.13$, $SD = 1.25$), suggesting the manipulation of objectification was successful.

An analysis of covariance with enjoyment of sexualization as a covariate was used to test Hypothesis 1 and 2. Results revealed an effect of objectification condition on participants' perception of the interaction as pleasant, $F(1, 88) = 21.76$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2 = .20$ (Figure 1), and time spent interacting with the confederate, $F(1, 88) = 3.88$, $p = .052$, $\eta^2 = .04$ (Figure 2). Consistent with hypotheses, women in the objectification condition perceived the interaction as less pleasant and interacted with the confederate for a shorter period of time than women in the control condition.

Finally, the indirect effect of condition on women's perception of the interaction as pleasant (Hypothesis 3) and time spent interacting (Hypothesis 4) through feelings of being objectified was examined using the Process Macro (Model 4; Hayes, 2018). Using bias-corrected and accelerated bootstrapping with 10,000 resamples, we estimated the indirect effect while controlling for enjoyment of sexualization. Results reported in Figure 3 revealed that consistent with Hypothesis 3, the degree of feeling objectified mediated the effect of condition on perceptions of pleasantness ($b = -.75$, $SE = 0.21$, 95% CI [-1.19, -.37]). Specifically, in the objectification condition, women reported feeling more objectified, which predicted perceptions of the interaction as less pleasant. Yet, contrary to Hypothesis 4, women's objectifying perceptions did not mediate the effect of condition on time spent talking with the confederate ($b = -2.58$, $SE = 2.86$, 95% CI [-8.68, 2.70]).

Discussion

The present study responds to recent calls to explore the process of objectification within actual interactions (Gervais et al., 2020). In particular, this study focused on how women interpret and respond to interpersonal experiences of objectification.

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The current work revealed that objectifying interactions with an unknown man led women to perceive the interaction as unpleasant and that these perceptions were mediated by women's perception of the confederate's behavior as objectifying. While inconsistent with some interaction research revealing that when objectified, women report increased desire to interact with an objectifying man (Gervais et al., 2011), this finding is in accordance with other interaction research showing that women report objectifying men as less likeable (Teng et al., 2015). What is clear is that how women perceive objectifying men is complicated. For instance, recent research emphasizes the importance of cognitive consistency in women's perceptions and responses to experiencing sexual objectification (Gervais, Allen, Riemer, & Gullickson, 2018). Because women may perceive experiences and sources of objectification differentially depending on their personal attitudes about being sexualized (Riemer et al., 2020), we controlled for women's enjoyment of sexualization.

Beyond perceptions, experiencing objectification directly reduced time women spent interacting with an objectifying man. Expanding work by Saguy and colleagues (2010), showing that a body focus decreased time women spent speaking when filmed, the current work revealed that in actual interactions, objectification has a detrimental effect on time women spend interacting with an objectifying man. Previous work has revealed that women self-silence by suppressing their thoughts and feelings in attempts to maintain relationships with men (Jack & Dill, 1992), with these behaviors explaining the link between women's sexist experiences and psychological distress (Hurst & Beesley, 2013). Although women's perceptions were unexpectedly not the mechanism by which objectification predicted decreased interaction times, this is in line with Saguy and colleagues' suggestion: "*women talk less when objectified because they attempt to align their behavior with what they assume is expected of them as sexual objects.*" (p. 5), or in other words women may not have interacted less because of behaviors men were engaging in, but because of expectations they

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perceived men had of them to act like sexual *objects*. While possible, it is also possible that in response to being objectified women felt angry and disgusted, so that termination of the interaction instead acted as an active confrontation response (Shepherd, 2019).

Limitations and future research

It is important to consider limitations of the present research. There was little variance explained by the analysis of covariance, suggesting the results are more exploratory than confirmatory in nature. Although the current work attempted to unpack the nuances of interpersonal objectifying experiences by controlling for women's enjoyment of sexualization, additional individual differences (e.g. previous victimization, sexual orientation) may play an important role, and should be assessed and examined in future work. Additionally, while the current work involved a commonly relied on interview context (e.g. Gervais et al., 2011) providing experimental control, it is possible power dynamics inherent within interviews may have shaped the extent to which women abided by perceived expectations regarding how to interact, suggesting that future research would benefit from not only examining how women perceive objectifying expectations, but also the dynamics involved. Importantly, these findings have implications for the workplace in which interviews are a necessary hiring component, and in which women must delicately balance abiding by gendered expectations and communicating their competency to do a job. We encourage future objectification research to expand upon this interactive work, while carefully considering the contexts of these interactions.

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Figure 1. Perceptions of the interaction as pleasant by condition.

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Figure 2. Time spent interacting by condition.

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Figure 3. Mediation model depicting indirect effect of objectification and perception of pleasantness through feeling of objectification.

Note. Standardized coefficient (standard error), controlling by ESS. * $p < .05$, $p < .01$.

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